

Aesthetics of Impermanence: Ryuichi Sakamoto's Async and Coda through Desmond's Otherness and Schopenhauer's Will

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Abstract

This paper explores the sonic framing of our being-towards-death and the ontological scarcity of the singular moment in Ryuichi Sakamoto's 2017 album *async* and its companion documentary *Coda*, in which he fundamentally transforms his approach to sound and time. Following the Fukushima nuclear disaster and a cancer diagnosis, Sakamoto abandoned the strict mathematical control and synthesizer mastery that defined his early electronic music and instead shifted towards a sound of natural decay and environmental noise. This paper interprets Sakamoto's aesthetic evolution as a direct challenge to Arthur Schopenhauer's philosophy of music. While Schopenhauer argued that aesthetic contemplation offers a necessary and temporary escape from the inherent suffering of the world (the Will), Sakamoto's *async* refuses to adhere to this aesthetic quietism by forcing the listener to dwell

within the world's materiality. Drawing also on William Desmond's concept of the *metaxu*, the intermediate space where the self and the "Other" meet, I argue that Sakamoto turns the reality of physical decay into a relationship of radical receptivity toward the world and provides the ground for an aesthetic encounter. By embracing the instrument's decay as an active expression of its own impermanence, and by allowing notes to naturally fade into the environment, and giving them the space and time to exist, *async* radically reframes mortality and the fleeting nature of sound. Rather than approaching entropy, death and decay as tragic phenomena that necessitate control or resolution through artistic intervention, Sakamoto affirms impermanence as a fundamental gift that opens the listener up to the porosity of being.

Keywords: *Ryuichi Sakamoto, asynchronism, impermanence, Arthur Schopenhauer, Metaxu, phenomenology of sound*

Introduction: The Asynchrony of Time and Eternity

“Time” is part of Sakamoto’s ongoing exploration of “asynchronism,” music arranged outside traditional time structures. Introduced on his 2017 album “async”, the concept was conceived as he recovered from his first bout with cancer — an experience that he has said newly honed his ear to the beauty of everyday sounds, both natural and man-made, sun showers and singing bowls.”

(Starnes, 2021)

When Ryuichi Sakamoto bowed the strings of a tsunami-wrecked piano in his documentary *Coda* (2017), he did more than record an instrument's last gasp; he revealed a metaphysics of sound. A central metaphor for the film and his 2017 album *async*, Sakamoto's exploration of metaphysical concepts such as decay, mortality, and the haunting beauty of impermanence proves to be a radical aesthetic experiment. Having to liberate music from time's linearity ("asynchronism") and to confront the "Otherness" of existence, whether in the eternal resonance of a singing bowl or the fractured silence of Fukushima. *async*, his post-cancer album, and *Coda*, its visual counterpart, explore the notion of both perpetual and impermanent sound. The former represents a sound that won't dissipate over time, revealing its nature as a metaphor for eternity, and the latter represents a sound that fades away, encapsulating the finite nature of existence. With a concept album such as *async* and its documentary counterpart, Sakamoto searches for the traces of sound, whether in the eternal resonance of a singing bowl or in the fractured silence of Fukushima.

This duality mirrors the tension at the heart of William Desmond's *metaxological* threshold. Here, art exists between Schopenhauer's suffering "will" (the impermanent sound as an emblem of life's fragility) and the transcendent "otherness" Desmond identifies in *Art, Origins, Otherness* (the eternal sound as a glimpse of the ungraspable). This neologism of Desmond's refers to a *logos*— word, discourse, account—of the *metaxu*—the between, the middle, the intermediate (Simpson, 2018). Sakamoto's *async* and his documentary *Coda*

reflect the line between metaphysics and art, where we see art negotiating with immanence and transcendence. Against Hegel's teleological *Absolute*, Sakamoto's work dwells in the threshold, where sound is neither mastered nor erased, but listened to, an act of artistic hospitality to what resists human control. This paper argues that Sakamoto's *async* constitutes a phenomenological refutation of Schopenhauer's pessimism. While Schopenhauer infers that music is a direct copy of the Will—and thus a confrontation with inherent suffering that requires some 'escape' through aesthetic contemplation—Sakamoto's late style proves that dwelling within that decay or impermanence is not suffering but an ethical encounter with "Otherness". By analyzing *async* through William Desmond's concept of *metaxu* (the between), I contend that Sakamoto transforms the Schopenhauerian struggle into a gift that redefines sonic decay not as a loss of the self, but as a hospitality to the porosity of being.

From Mastery to Porosity: The Phenomenological Turn

"Even in today's world of amusing ourselves to death, taking pleasure in ugliness and being rampant with impetuosity and desire, there is such an old man who is able to listen to the sound (social voice, natural sound) and create music with pure feelings" (Guo, 2019).

Arguably one of the most influential and well-known Japanese artists, Ryuichi Sakamoto, started his career in the early 1970s with his

collaboration with Haruomi Hosono and Yukihiro Takahashi. This collaboration led to the formation of their electronic band called Yellow Magic Orchestra, in 1978. Even though he was still part of the trio, Sakamoto released his first solo album, *Thousand Knives of Ryuichi Sakamoto*, in mid-1978. Each of *Thousand Knives*' six pieces swerves with a deft touch through complex arrangements, playful voicings, and cheeky key changes, says Daniel Martin-McCornick (2019). This first album reveals an enduring fascination with nature's fragile complexity, where crystalline sonic architecture mirrors ecosystems, and industrial tones seek uneasy reconciliation with what remains organic. When Sakamoto started recording his first solo album, China was only two years removed from the end of the three-decade reign of Mao Zedong (Pedersen, 2019). The album starts with Sakamoto reading a poem from 1928 by Mao, describing his first experience with this theory of guerrilla warfare. Sakamoto's decision to start the album with Mao's poem reflects the intrinsic nature of having to face an overwhelming force. Having to find temporary respite in aesthetic experience and the persistent engagement with external pressures and internal states emerges as a fundamental and evolving theme throughout Sakamoto's artistic life and career. Exploring the tension arising from the unfolding, often challenging reality of the work and his endeavor to find shelter in the personal, internalized resolution lays the groundwork, especially in his magnum opus *async*. Evidently, it can be inferred from Sakamoto's decision to start his first album with the

line "the foe encircles us thousands strong," which encapsulates a struggle to harmonize with external forces. This adversarial relationship with the world mirrors Schopenhauer's depiction of the Will, which posits that the innermost nature of existence is not peace, but a restless, opposing drive:

"Thus a constant struggle is carried on between life and death, the main result whereof is the resistance by which that striving, which constitutes the innermost nature of everything, is everywhere impeded. It presses and urges in vain; yet, by reason of its inner nature, it cannot cease." (Schopenhauer, 1818/1966).

In this passage, Schopenhauer identifies the ground of existence not as a rational order, but as a blind, irrational striving. If the "innermost nature" of the world is characterized by this chaotic force pressing forward "in vain", then the artist's role becomes an attempt to impose form onto that chaos. This framework illuminates Sakamoto's early reliance on the synthesizer. Unlike acoustic instruments, which are bound by the material resistance and natural decay Schopenhauer describes, the synthesizer offers the possibility of total regulation. It is what allows the artist to superimpose a mathematical schema onto the Will, effectively attempting to negate the material resistance of nature by replacing it with a purely rational, controlled form.

Reflecting this metaphysical tension, the initial album encapsulates the juxtaposition of two conflicting impulses: the external clamor of a world in discord and the internal yearning for transient

harmony. This rupture in this philosophy of control occurs through the dual crises of the Fukushima nuclear disaster and Sakamoto's diagnosis with oropharyngeal cancer in 2014, causing him to take a year-long break from music and any artistic endeavor. This biological and environmental collapse forces a movement away from a culture of distraction to a confrontation with the "social voice and natural sound" (Guo, 2019). The cancer diagnosis, which later returned in 2021, strips Sakamoto's illusion of physical permanence. His subsequent work, including *The Revenant* (2015) and his activism regarding Fukushima, moves beyond the simple binary of man versus nature. Instead of warning that "keeping silent after Fukushima is barbaric" (Yamaguchi & Kageyama, 2023) solely as a political statement, Sakamoto began to embody this lack of silence in his soundscapes. He transitioned from the synthesizer – an instrument of infinite sustains and control – to the tsunami wrecked piano, an instrument defined by its brokenness.

This late aesthetic turn creates the framework for analyzing *async* (2017). It represents a departure from the synchronicity of his early pop-electronic work, which sought to master time, toward and asynchronism that allows the Otherness of nature to speak. By the time of his death in 2023, Sakamoto had moved from the mathematical structures of *Thousand Knives* to a living dialogue between art and existence. Thus, Sakamoto's legacy remains a rich one, resonating with profound meditation on the human condition. A career that not only sticks to music but tries to transcend its boundaries to

become a living dialogue between art and existence. From his albums and film scores to immersive exhibitions and avant-garde operas, Sakamoto crafts a phenomenology of immersion. Interrogating temporal decay and the subject's position within the natural world, his work does not seek to transcend time but to re-inhabit it. This shift lays the groundwork for challenging Schopenhauer's pessimism: rather than escaping the Will, the late Sakamoto dwells within the traces of the world, finding in the impermanent body not a source of suffering, but a site of porosity. As for Schopenhauer, the aesthetic experience is predicated on a negation of the Will, which serves as a momentary cessation of the blind striving that characterizes existence. In this view, art serves as a form of asceticism, allowing the subject to step out of the stream of time to avoid suffering. Sakamoto's late work, however, rejects this escapism. He locates the aesthetic moment not in the suspension of time, but in the affirmation of entropy. This turn toward entropy is not just a concept but the structural engine of his late style, manifesting directly in two works that systematically dismantle our desire for order.

async (2017) and Coda (2017) as Case Studies: Embodying Impermanence and Letting Go

async is Sakamoto's nineteenth solo studio album, released in 2017. The album's main idea was to explore the comfort that human nature finds in synchronicity. In a 2017 interview after the release of the album, Sakamoto explains:

“That’s why I wanted to create untraditional music that doesn’t synchronize, [because it’s like] speaking in a language that doesn’t exist.” (art/research, 2017).

His whole ambition during the totality of his career was to break the stereotypical prejudice paradigm and boundaries and learn how to see things upside down (Saxelby, 2016). Even though all the sounds make up a whole, they never create a proper sense of harmony. The album opens with *andata*. A hauntingly beautiful track that introduces us to the first strokes of the piano. Wrapped in sheets of reverb and plucked tones, the entirety of the track incorporates the piano’s sound that turns into an organ melody bristling with distortion. It also introduces the soundscape, which is marked by deliberate gaps between the notes. Then comes a disruptive and loud soundscape marked by the organ. The melody gets disrupted by the other tracks of the album, such as *disintegration* and *tri*. Marked by their dissonance, they evoke a sense of rupture while still maintaining a sense of ambient sound in the background. *Solari*, the third track of the album, invites comparison with *Solaris*, Andrei Tarkovsky’s 1972 masterpiece. Near the center of the album, Sakamoto confronts mortality itself. *Life, Life*, and *fullmoon*, represent the gentle movement of death and impermanence. With poems read by David Sylvian and Paul Bowles, both these tracks encapsulate our eternal conflict with what remains to be the heaviest of all, death. In *fullmoon*, we hear Paul Bowles, one of the greatest 20th-century American novelists, cite a poem from Bernardo Bertolucci’s *The Sheltering Sky*. The

score of the movie was originally composed primarily by Sakamoto. At the end of the movie, Bowles himself narrated an excerpt of the novel, and Sakamoto used this narration:

“Because we don’t know when we will die. We get to think of life as an inexhaustible well. Yet everything happens only a certain number of times. And a very small number, really. How many more times will you remember a certain afternoon of your childhood. Some afternoon that is so deeply a part of your being that you can’t even conceive your life without it? Perhaps four or five times more. Perhaps not even that. How many more times will you watch the full moon rise. Perhaps twenty, and yet it all seems limitless.” (Sakamoto, 2017)

This narration functions as a sonic *memento mori*, which strips away the illusion of the “inexhaustible well” to expose the ontological scarcity of the singular moment. Whereas Schopenhauer’s Will is characterized by a blind and infinite striving that disregards the individual, Bowles’ text and Sakamoto’s sonic framing of it enact a limit and force a confrontation with the finite nature of “being-towards-death”. The question “how many more times?” dissolves the abstraction of time, which renders each remaining moment not as a repetition but as a singular and vanishing gift. For Sakamoto, writing in the shadow of his diagnosis, this passage transforms the listener’s experience from passive hearing to an urgent, ethical attentiveness to the present and reframes time here

not as an open horizon but as a finite series of irreversible events. To amplify this universality, Sakamoto adds ten different languages, all reciting the same extract. He expresses that even though what is being recited is the same, holding the same meaning, we hear ten different sounds. Paul Bowles' voice is set against a backdrop of sinewaves, bowed cymbal, and spare piano as other voices gather around it (坂本龍一 (*Ryuichi Sakamoto*) – *Fullmoon*, 2017). *Life, Life*, on the other hand, has David Sylvian reading a poem written by Arseny Tarkovsky, the father of Andrei Tarkovsky. “And all will be repeated, all be re-embodied/You will dream everything I have seen in dream,” Sylvian narrates, “Dreams, reality, death, on wave after wave.” This album is the representation of the inexhaustible well of existentialism. We see the remnants of death as compositional grammar. With *fullmoon*'s poem, there is a sonic memento mori “How many more times will you watch the full moon rise?”, asking us to remember that we have to die. A Heideggerian approach, the soundscape of *async* reflects our being-towards-death, and sounds out its shape. The spare piano and bowed cymbal in *fullmoon* represent emptiness as presence and death's shadow in sound (see Figure 1).

Figure 1

Album cover of async (2017)

The documentary film *Ryuichi Sakamoto: CODA*, directed by Stephen Nomura Schible, was released in Japan in November 2017. The documentary was shot and edited in a span of five years, from 2012 to 2017. A thorough representation of Sakamoto's life and works, and his battle and reconciliation with getting diagnosed with cancer. The documentary maps out Sakamoto's intentions in creating his 2017 album *async*. He explains in the documentary that there are countless sounds in the world, but we do not perceive these sounds as music, claiming that he has a strong desire to combine these sounds with his own work. However, in reality, these sounds have their own musical resonance. We learn that Sakamoto's endeavor is to create a sound order by combining them with instruments. A blend of sounds that has the characteristic of disorder as well as unity. The documentary opens with Sakamoto visiting the restricted contamination zone in Fukushima, recording and playing the piano wrecked by the tsunami. A combination of what used to be and what will be. During the documentary, we see Sakamoto's creative journey

and artistic practice. He plays with sounds, singing bowls, recording rain sounds, and using instruments in various ways to find the sound of the album. While walking through the forest and the remains of Fukushima, Sakamoto records his footsteps, later becoming the fifth song on the album, *walker*. An insight into his creative process and his battle with cancer, *Coda* gives us a sonic testament to the courage of fragility. This cinematic and sonic evidence prepares the ground for rigorous philosophical interrogation. If *Coda* visualizes the artist's surrender to the sounds of the world, to the tsunami, cancer, and the rain, it simultaneously challenges the dominant 19th-century metaphysical framework for understanding music: Schopenhauer's pessimism. While Schopenhauer argued that music is the direct copy of the Will's suffering, requiring the listener to transcend the physical world, Sakamoto's method suggests the opposite. The courage of fragility witnessed in *Coda* demands that we do not transcend the material world but descend further into it.

The Will's Resonance – Schopenhauer in *Async* and *Coda* (Sound as Suffering)

How does Sakamoto's *async* come into play as a counterexample to Schopenhauer's musical metaphysics? *async* can be regarded as a rupture in traditional musical metaphysics, laying the groundwork that the Will can be grounded in material decay and temporal fragility, thus transforming aesthetic contemplation into an encounter with impermanence. Schopenhauer established art as a form of knowledge where

aesthetic perception bypasses ordinary, suffering-laden experience to attend to the permanent Platonic Ideas, or, in the case of music, the Will itself. Music, being the highest art form, provides a temporary release from the incessant pain associated with the unfulfilled desires of the Will, offering access to a will-less and timeless subject of knowledge. It is in the *World as Will and Representation* that Schopenhauer posits that aesthetic contemplation provides a temporary release from the suffering of the everyday world and the demands of the individual will. Borrowing from Kant, Schopenhauer establishes that all things have will as their essential nature. This nature, as we've previously mentioned, results in the lack of fulfillment, incorporating a telos in our nature that needs to transcend ordinary forms of perception. In light of this suffering, as Dale Jacquette underlines, the pleasure of aesthetic contemplation is a relief from the incessant pain of the inevitably unfulfilled desires associated with ordinary consciousness of the manifold particulars of quotidian experience (Jacquette, 2003). Aesthetic contemplation allows a move towards a will-less and timeless subject of knowledge, as Schopenhauer puts it, and access to Platonic Ideas, escaping the Will's demands and losing ourselves in art and nature. This aesthetic rescue is made possible because art reveals the hierarchy of the Will's objectification, bridging the gap between blind striving and intelligible form. Desmond articulates this structural function of art, noting that:

“Will in itself is not a static substance but a dynamic power that objectifies itself at

different grades that, he tells us, correspond to different Platonic Ideas. The Artwork serves to lift the mind to the contemplation of the Platonic Ideas” (Desmond, 2018).

As Desmond interprets, Schopenhauer’s aesthetics represent an escape from immanence, because this aesthetic contemplation offers a temporary release from the transient reality of the Will and the phenomenal world by ascending to the realm of timeless, permanent Ideas. The temporary release from suffering is best put into action by music, which is the highest form, according to Schopenhauer. He argues that music is not merely a copy of the Ideas but rather is a direct copy or immediate objectification of the Will itself. Music speaks of the “essence” of the world, embodying the Will’s most secret history, including states like suffering, sorrow, and pain. The world of nature, as the immediate representation of the thing-in-itself, represents the immediate affirmation of certain states in which we feel sorrow, joy, or any other feeling that we experience when we hear Beethoven’s symphony, for example. There is no intermediary in the sense that we experience conceptual mediation. Music becomes reality’s revelation, confronting the raw pulse of existence. As Jacquette also states, this internal friction grants the subject a unique form of access to the Will, distinguishing the immediate, felt experience of pain from the detached observation of external objects:

“Suffering is nonrepresentational, according to Schopenhauer, in the sense that it does not

depict the phenomenal world. When we suffer pain or frustrations of desire, the experience of suffering by itself, unlike perception, is not a representation of the phenomenal world. To suffer is therefore to experience nonrepresentational reality as intimately as possible within the confines of empirical psychology” (Jacquette, 2003).

Consequently, if suffering is the only experience that bypasses the filter of representation, then music, which is Schopenhauer’s copy of the Will itself, functions as its sonic equivalent. Unlike the visual arts, which offer the safety distance of an object to contemplate, music dissolves the gap between subject and object. It does not depict pain but enacts it. Music then forces the listener into an immediate, unprotected confrontation with the Will, mirroring the non-representational immediacy of suffering itself.

Comparing Ryuichi Sakamoto’s album *async* to Schopenhauer’s Will, the album’s restless melodies and unresolved tensions become aural metaphors for the Will’s “constant struggle,” where even moments of repose (a fragile piano phrase, a suspended chord) are haunted by the knowledge of their impermanence. However, in this work, Sakamoto diverges from Schopenhauer’s pessimism. His music does not merely lament the struggle; rather, it orchestrates it, transforming discord into a compositional principle. In this manner, the artist’s inaugural work foreshadows the existential themes of *async*, where the decay of the tsunami piano, the howl of Fukushima’s winds, and

the silence between notes would later articulate a lifetime's meditation on resistance, resilience, and the fleeting beauty of equilibrium. Even though Schopenhauer's aesthetic contemplation offers release from the Will's striving, Sakamoto's *async* forces us to dwell in the Will's materiality.

Music Beyond Representation

What is then the musician's specific role in expressing the Will? For Schopenhauer, the musician possesses the terrifying power of immediate knowledge. While other arts speak only of appearances (shadows) of the world, music speaks of the essence (the Will itself). However, this immediacy comes at a cost, as the aesthetic genius suffers precisely because their sensitivity makes them transparent to the Will's torment. As Jacquette (2003) argues, "The artist's heroism lies in the persistence of such action in the face of such content: he himself bears the cost of producing that play; he himself is the will objectifying itself and remaining in constant suffering". In this framework, the musician is a tragic hero who imposes aesthetic form upon the chaotic, suffering Will. It is also worth noting that this tension also mirrors Kant's own anxiety regarding the wildness of the genius. In *The Critique the Power of Judgment*, Kant defines genius as:

"Genius is the talent (natural gift) that gives the rule to art. Since the talent, as an inborn productive faculty of the artist, itself belongs to nature, this could also be expressed thus: Genius is the inborn predisposition of the mind (ingenium) through which nature gives

the rule to art." (Kant, 1790/2000, p. 186 [5:307])

Meaning that the genius acts as an intermediary for an originating power that rational concepts cannot fully grasp. Yet Kant feared the darkness of this "originating nature" (Kant, 1790/2000, p. 186 [5:307]), famously warning that genius threatens to degenerate into "nothing but a madness" without the "discipline" of taste to clip its wings (p. 197 [5:319]). For Kant, the terror of the sublime is ultimately resolved through subreption; that is, attributing the power of the object to the subject, thereby affirming the moral subject's superiority over nature. Schopenhauer, however, strips this Enlightenment optimism away. He leaves the musician to bear the terror of the Will without conquering it. Sakamoto's *async* locates itself there: not in the Kantian mastery of the will, but in the madness of the untamed piano.

There are various ways in which musicians and artists decide to represent what needs to be represented. With *async*, Sakamoto dismantles the heroic narrative and instead of imposing order upon the Will, he engages in a phenomenological surrender to it. This surrender manifests not only as a metaphysical stance but as a concrete attentiveness to the fragile material world that sustains us. Sakamoto, a huge advocate for climate change and against nuclear power, finds his inspiration in the everyday. However, besides the beauty in everyday life, music can also reflect historical and cultural experiences of suffering, such as the history of the Fukushima disaster.

Sakamoto's music, particularly in conjunction with other arts like tragedy, can bring subjects face-to-face with the realities of life and the suffering inherent in existence. This shift is most vividly embodied in his use of the tsunami piano:

“I went to see one of those pianos drowned in tsunami water near Fukushima, and recorded it,” he said. “Of course, it was totally out of tune, but I thought it was beautiful. I thought: ‘Nature tuned it.’” Parts of these sounds are on “*async*” (Beta, 2017).

This statement marks a radical departure from Schopenhauer. As Schopenhauer views the Will as a constant struggle that must be quieted by aesthetic contemplation, Sakamoto views the tsunami's destruction of the piano's industrial tuning not as damage, but as a “retuning” by the natural work. This dissonance is no longer a representation of human suffering; it is exactly the infra-ordinary sound of the world returning to its elemental state. Specifically, in *async*, Sakamoto embraces noise, glitches, and environmental sounds. It destabilizes the very idea of musical “purity.” Embodying the vernacular beauty and environmental noises, Sakamoto does not shy away from confronting us with sound *as sound*, stripping Schopenhauer's biases. Vernacular, everyday beauty can be expressed as something that we no longer see. It is *par essence* what functions in the background, a structure of our life that we do not notice. We often pay attention to the opposite of the *infra-ordinaire* and focus on the *extra-ordinaire*. Sakamoto defies that and makes it so that the inexhaustible beauty of

the everyday does not lose its capacity to reveal deeper truths about decay and the haunting beauty of impermanence, its power to challenge conventional notions of musical purity and aesthetic hierarchy, or its inherent significance when approached through attentive, unbiased listening, allowing us to encounter sound for itself. This is also explored in George Perec's conception of art and aesthetics. His call to action is to explore environmental aesthetics, to notice our surroundings, as there are things that have not been considered in accordance with aesthetics.

This philosophical commitment also extended beyond the studio. Sakamoto speaks of nature and our governance over it in his documentary, and this fascination with sonic decay extended specifically beyond the tsunami piano's history. In 2019, Sakamoto placed a piano in his New York backyard to weather the elements, documenting its gradual return to nature. This experiment, like the tsunami piano, rejects the teleology of the instrument (which is designed to hold a specific pitch) in favor of the entropy of the environment. In doing so, Sakamoto suggests that the suffering of the Will is only suffering if we insist on mastering it. If we accept the nature tuning, *per se*, the struggle dissolves into a vernacular beauty. This piano is also integrated into the poster of an exhibition, following the format of his album *async* (see Figure 2).

Figure 2

Exhibition poster for Ryuichi Sakamoto | seeing sound, hearing time

Note. From Wang (n.d.),

<https://viktorwang.com/Ryuichi-Sakamoto>

The Perpetual Sound Paradox

“I think of music from the perspective of the piano. The piano does not keep the note long. When we let go, the sound dilutes and disappears. You can still hear a very small amount. But the noise around you drowns it out. The thought of a voice that remains constant puts me under its spell. A sound that time cannot destroy” (Schible, 2017).

Sakamoto’s lament, a yearning for a sound that time cannot destroy. A longing for a voice that remains constant amid entropy. An impossible desire that reveals certain tensions. His own compositions on *async* unveil mirroring concepts such as decay, yet we see Sakamoto yearning for permanence. The very idea of the paradox of the perpetual sound can be fully illustrated with *fullmoon*. The poem recited by Bowles, “How many more times,” reflects time’s

scarcity composed into sound. This quote evokes the theme of finite time, with “perhaps twenty”, contrasted with the perception or feeling of limitlessness or eternity, with the line “And yet it all seems limitless.” The perpetual sound that Sakamoto seeks is nevertheless not immortality; he comes to terms with his own mortality in the documentary but desires what Desmond calls “the gift of hearing time itself, an echo that persists precisely because it fades.” *Async* represents that echo; it lets its sound be its own ruin.

Ars longa, vita brevis, art is long, time is short, represents the core paradox explored by Sakamoto in *async*. His lament about the piano note’s decay represents the “*vita brevis*” aspect, the inherent impermanence of sound and of individual existence, and the temporal world. The sire for a “voice that remains constant” is the yearning for “*ars longa*”, a sound or creation that defies time and entropy. Even the act of placing a piano outdoors to succumb to the elements highlights Sakamoto’s direct engagement with impermanence. After contemplating his documentary *Coda*, it is clear that his illness and contemplation of mortality further underscored the transient nature of life and led him to embrace aesthetics like *wabi-sabi*, finding beauty in simplicity and focusing on the weight of each sound.

The contradiction in Schopenhauer’s aesthetics is clear here. As music is the purest objectification of the Will, a direct and timeless expression, why does Sakamoto’s longing for a sound that time cannot destroy feel so urgent? Schopenhauer’s timeless

Ideas render impermanence irrelevant, while Sakamoto's work depends on it. The perpetual sound that Sakamoto desires is nevertheless impossible; however, that very impossibility becomes the art. However, if the will-less aesthetic experience allows access to the Platonic Ideas, revealing these enduring Ideas or directly embodying the Will without its suffering, offers a glimpse of something akin to "*ars longa*" amidst the fleeting pain of "*vita brevis*."

Threshold of Otherness – Desmond's Gift in Sakamoto's Sound (Impermanence as Gift)

Examining Sakamoto's *async*, we can see how sound is employed to navigate complex notions and thresholds, embodying a dialogue with the "Otherness" of existence. As aesthetics are not simply just a matter of distinctive and autonomous concern but have a leak in the whole of human existence, Desmond's *metaxu* (the "between"), the space where self and other meet, transforms impermanence from scarcity into generosity. This also manifests itself in Sakamoto's *aysnc*, with the decaying pianos and field recordings. Sakamoto allures us with the beauty of the tsunami piano's dissonance, turning it into a gift of attention.

According to Desmond, the notion of beauty has *par essence*, a gift character; so much so that we are struck by it. It opens us up before we open ourselves up. It establishes an element of rapport between ourselves and what is other, and we are taken outside of ourselves by the very first

encounter that we have with the beautiful. The notion of gift is crucial is both Desmond's philosophy and Sakamoto's intentions in his music. What strikes as the distinguishing element in Desmond's philosophy is the "Impermanence as Gift." Unlike beliefs that might consider impermanence as only decay or ugliness, Desmond puts it into a framework that allows for perceiving value and beauty in the transient, just like Sakamoto.

"...music is perhaps the most powerful art to return us to the porosity, while at the same time moving a *passio essendi*, prior to any rationalization of the movement of desire, and exceeding complete self-determination of it. We do not first move, we are moved" (Desmond, 2018).

With music, we are plunged into a variety of experiences, whether it be temporal or metaphysical. A certain recollection of eternity in time, the secret relation between death is offered to us. As previously touched upon, Desmond talks about the "porosity" power that music has, a unique power to return us to a fundamental state. This is an original openness of being that exceeds rational control. An ontological condition in which we are first moved by the world before we have any sense of rationalizing it. Sakamoto's sound in *async* can be interpreted as engaging this *passio essendi* with its focus on decay and environmental noise. Sakamoto tries to resonate with the elemental experience of existence, without trying to overcome or rationalize it. As we've previously examined, the

decaying piano in *andata* or the Fukushima field recordings are not conventionally beautiful, but they do strike us with their raw presence. Sakamoto offers us a gift of sound *as sound*.

Metaxu of Decay: Sakamoto's Piano as Threshold

The transition from suffering to gift is physically embodied in the instrument of the piano. In Desmond's philosophy, the *metaxu* is the between, the intermediate space where the self and the Other meet. The tsunami piano serves as the ultimate *metaxu* in Sakamoto's oeuvre.

From a Schopenhauerian perspective, the piano's brokenness is a testament to the violence of the Will – a struggle where nature crushes artifice. However, through Desmond, the piano's destruction renders it porous. Meaning that the tsunami stripped the instrument of its industrial autonomy (its ability to hold a fixed, man-made pitch) and forced it into a dialogue with nature. When Sakamoto plays this instrument, he is not mastering a tool; he is, in fact, collaborating with a ruin. The dissonance that strikes the listener is what Desmond calls the gift character of beauty; it opens us up before we open ourselves up.

The shock of the out-of-tune string in *async* bypasses our rational expectation for harmony, returning us to a fundamental state of listening. In this specific *metaxu* of decay, the boundary between the artist and the disaster dissolves. The gift that Sakamoto offers is not a polished melody but rather the raw presence of the "Other" residing in the

instrument. By allowing the piano to speak its own ruin, Sakamoto turns the terror of the sublime that Kant refers to and the suffering of the Will into an act of gratitude for the fragile, fleeting "miracle of the is that is given" (Desmond, 2003). He shows that to be broken is not to be destroyed, but rather to be opened.

Spatializing the Metaxu: The Quest for Perpetual Sound

A counterpart to Sakamoto's album and documentary, the exhibition "Ryuichi Sakamoto |seeing sound, hearing time" was held at the Museum of Contemporary Art Tokyo until March 2025. One of the most prominent imageries in Sakamoto's works, the piano recovered from a school devastated by the 2011 Great East Japan Earthquake tsunami can be seen in the photograph above. The imagery of the decaying piano remains to be one of the most concrete examples in Sakamoto's attempts to portray the impermanence of sound and life:

"It was the piano in the ruins that was the clue throughout the themes of this documentary: anti-nuclear energy development, reverence for original music of nature, unyieldingness during the anti-cancer period, and love for music"(Guo, 2019).

This meditation on material fragility is further spatialized in his partnership with Shiro Takatani, where the solitary object of the piano is expanded into an immersive environment that interrogates the nature of time (see Figure 3).

Figure 3

*Installation view of async-immersion tokyo (2024),
Ryuichi Sakamoto & Shiro Takatani, Museum of
Contemporary Art Tokyo*

Note. Photograph by Takeshi Asano.

After his 2017 album *Async*, Sakamoto presented it at an exhibition at Tokyo's Watari Museum of Contemporary Art. Sakamoto himself called it "installation music" in an interview with *Bijutsu Techo* magazine, expressing that his aim was to immerse people in the sounds in an environment that is the same as the one he had while listening and creating. The exhibition integrated space and visual elements, allowing visitors to experience how sound resonates and transforms within space. The exhibition being centered around his 2017 album *async*, Sakamoto transforms music's medium. Highlighting the difference between listening to an album and experiencing it. Incorporating audio-visual installations such as *LIFE – fluid, invisible, inaudible (2007/2021)*, "the work contains two important sub-currents: the breaking of the unilateral experience opera, here

achieved through the recreating and deconstructing of Sakamoto's 1999 opera *LIFE*. And secondly, the integration of technology, image, and nature to achieve what Sakamoto calls the 'interstices of sound and image', here configured by the experience of walking through a Japanese garden" (Wang, n.d.; see Figure 4).

Figure 4

*LIFE – fluid, invisible, inaudible...
(2007/2021), installation view, by
Ryuichi Sakamoto & Shiro Takatani, M
WOODS Hutong, Beijing.*

Where *async* sonically captures impermanence through decaying tones, and *Coda* frames the disaster's aftermath, the outdoor piano becomes a living installation. The string, warped by rain and frost and resonating unpredictably with the wind, captures nature's music. Embodying the dichotomy between human artifice and natural entropy. Sakamoto's work literalized Hegel's doctrines concerning art. Wanting art to be for itself and yet knowing that art cannot continue to live only by itself. "If it is to be great it must have an openness

that makes home for all the major importances of the human being” (Desmond, 2003). Even though Desmond tries to capture Hegel’s theories about architecture and purpose here, we see Sakamoto also trying to establish a harmonious existence between space and sound, between the abstract and the concrete. “The singular harmonious wholeness of a great work”, underlines Desmond. Prominent imagery of nature is used by Sakamoto to create atmospheric textures, whether it be in his installations or his compositions. The piano, being one of the strongest metaphors for eternity, beams in his album *async*. Echoing, reverberating, and gradually fading into the surrounding environment, the piano symbolizes eternity. “Observing the piano’s transient nature, with its sound gradually fading into the surrounding environment, Sakamoto felt a longing, admiring instruments like the guitar or violin for their ability to sustain sound. Motivated by this, he committed to the quest for the perpetual sound, complementing the flow of film and adding a touch of vibrancy” (Venzheha, 2025).

Conclusion

“We hear it calling too with the works of great musicians, like Mozart, when they disappear in the sounding of the music itself. No God need be named, but some music is so mysteriously intimate with the porosity of being that we are awakened beyond ourselves, as if released into a kind of praying.” (Desmond, 2003).

Sakamoto’s most striking image, the decay of the piano’s sound, grapples with the transient nature of things. The sound merges with its surroundings,

highlighting the sonic impermanence inherent in the instrument’s existence in time. The Japanese idiom “Mono no Aware” (物寂し) resonates deeply with the awareness of impermanence. The deep, gentle sadness associated with the passing and changing nature of all things is a key element in understanding Japanese aesthetics, just as it is central to understanding music’s role in grappling with concepts such as time and eternity. Reflecting simplicity, imperfection, and the transient nature of existence. Sakamoto’s exploration of sound, from its inevitable decay to the aspiration for its perpetuation, provides a modern artistic lens through which to view the age-old paradox of *Ars longa, vita brevis*. His work does not resolve this tension but inhabits it, finding beauty in impermanence and glimpsing eternity within the transient. By embracing decay and seeking perpetual sound, drawing on philosophical insights into the nature of Will, Otherness, and the porous “between,” Sakamoto leaves behind a powerful meditation on life, death, and the enduring, transcendent capacity of art. Speaking near the end of his life, reflecting on his mortality and his creative drive, Sakamoto articulated this tension himself:

“I honestly don’t know how many years I have left. It could be 20 years, 10 years, or a relapse reduces it to just one. I am not taking anything for granted. But I know that I want to make more music. Music that I won’t be ashamed to leave behind — meaningful work.” (Starnes, 2021).

Ultimately, this meaningful work serves as his final act of porosity; a sonic proof that by ceasing to fight the constant struggle of the Will, the artists does not disappear into silence, but is released, as Desmond suggests, into the enduring prayer of the music itself.

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